

IOS AND ANDROID GRADING APPLICATION: INNOVATIVE ASSESSMENT TOOL ON NEW NORMAL OF EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to identify the use of iOS and Android grading application as an innovative assessment tool among Grade 8 students in Mataasnakahoy NHS in the S.Y. 2019-2020. In line with the Interim Guidelines for Assessment and Grading in Light of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan, the researcher utilizes this application to administer the written works that are given to the students every quarter and grade their summative assessments which are used to report their achievement. Descriptive quantitative type of research was utilized and survey questionnaire was the main instrument in data gathering. There is a high extent on the use of iOS and Android grading application that affects the students in terms of applicability and adaptability, assessment and motivation, and ease of use. One hundred thirty-two out of one hundred eighty students in Grade 8 in the aforementioned school had been chosen. The content is limited only on the use of ZipGrade application on Mathematics subject of the students where the researcher is their subject teacher. The different problems encountered by the students are the hardship in answering on ZipGrade answer sheet and the difficulty in seeing which item is incorrectly answered. This study utilized an action plan to solve these problems which is to maximize its use as an innovative assessment tool on Education's New Normal. The action plan focuses on the objectives on coping with specific structure and features of ZipGrade answer sheet and providing an alternative copy of ZipGrade answer sheet. Each objective contains two activities that are aligned on the latest trend of Education. The importance of this paper is to enlighten other educators on the essence of using iOS and Android grading application as an innovative assessment tool for the students' examinations.

Keywords: ZipGrade, ZipGrade answer sheet, iOS and Android grading application, Raosoft Database Management System, Philippines